

Journal of Geographical Research: Oceans

Supporting Information for

Quantifying the mean sea level, tide, and surge contributions to changing coastal high water levels

*Authors: Karen Palmer*¹, Christopher S. Watson¹, Hannah E. Power², and John R. Hunter³.*

Affiliations:

¹School of Geography, Planning, and Spatial Sciences, University of Tasmania, Hobart TAS 7005

²School of Environmental and Life Sciences, University of Newcastle, Callaghan NSW 2308

³Institute of Marine and Antarctic Studies, University of Tasmania, Hobart TAS 7005

* Corresponding author: Karen Palmer (karen.palmer@utas.edu.au)

Guide to Supporting Information

This document is presented as an index to the additional resources archived at www.zenodo.org. The Supporting Information referred to in the main paper includes:

- 1) Demonstration code (MATLAB Live Script) for practical demonstration of the operations involved in computing the total High Water level probabilities.
- 2) Figures 2-4 from the main paper for all 166 sites in the study.
- 3) A complete table of all exceedance results.

The code, figures, and table of results can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12597330>.

1. Demonstration code

The demonstration script computes the probability distributions of separated sea level components (mean sea level, predicted HW tide, and HW skew surges), their joint probability, and statistics. Figures 2, 3, and 4 from the main paper are reproduced using data from the Port Kembla tide gauge ([Bureau of Meteorology: Australian](#)

[Baseline Sea Level Monitoring Project](#)). This code is provided to demonstrate the method, not as a self-contained toolbox. Input variables are specified from outputs produced by the [Tide Peaks Toolbox](#) available from MATLAB File Exchange.

The demonstration code and the files required to execute the **.mlx** Live Script in MATLAB are contained in the zip folder **JPMMdemo** as follows:

📁 **JPMMdemo.zip**

- **mlx_JPMMdemo.mlx**: MATLAB Live Script demonstration code
- **portkembla.mat**: mat-file of tide gauge data used in demo
- **stat.m**: m-file function produces table of statistics from input variable
- **statpdf.m**: m-file function produces table from input distribution

The **.mlx** Live Script is executed in MATLAB from the same directory containing the required files. Output files are saved to the same directory. The demonstration outputs produced include the following files:

- **Fig2_MSL_Port Kembla.jpg**
- **Fig3_tide+surge_E1_Port Kembla.jpg**
- **Fig3_tide+surge_E2_Port Kembla.jpg**
- **Fig4_JPMM_Port Kembla.jpg**
- **portkembla.mat**

2. Figures 2-4 for 166 study sites

Figures 2-4 in the main paper, as output from the demonstration code, illustrate the methods for deriving the total High Water level distributions by the Joint Probability of Maxima Method described. Figure 2 in Section 2.3 illustrates the MSL component distribution ($P_{z_0}(z)$) for the two 19-year epochs. Figure 3 in Section 2.4 illustrates the joint tide and surge component distribution ($P_{t+s}(z)$) from the sum of monthly distributions, accounting for seasonal variation. Figure 4 in Section 2.6 illustrates the total High Water level distribution ($P_{\xi}(z)$), from which the frequency-based thresholds and exceedances are estimated. In the main paper, examples are shown from Cambridge, USA, and Port Kembla, Australia.

The equivalent figures for all 166 study sites are organised by dataset in subfolders as follows:

- 📁 **GESLA_JPMM.zip**
 - 📁 **Fig2_MSL**
 - 📁 **Fig3_tidesurge**
 - 📁 **Fig4_JPMM**
- 📁 **BoM_JPMM.zip**

- 📁 **Fig2_MSL**
- 📁 **Fig3_tidesurge**
- 📁 **Fig4_JPMM**

Each figure is supplied as a 300 dpi resolution png image file, named as follows:

Figure 2: **Fig2_MSL_dataset_sitename_country.png**

Figure 3: **Fig3_tide+surge_Epoch_sitename_country.png**

Figure 4: **Fig4_JPMM_sitename_country.png**

3. Table of results

The table of results contained in the **Results** subfolder is an Excel **.xlsx** spreadsheet, with exceedance statistics listed for each site. The sites are listed in groups by ocean region, from north to south, matching the plot order from left to right shown in Figures 5 (a, b, and c) and 7 (a and b) in the main paper. The table variables, including 56 columns, are as follows:

- **Plot order** – numbered from left to right.
- **Region** - ocean regions as labelled in Figure 1 in the main paper.
- **Country** – three-letter country codes (ISO 3166-1 alpha-3).
- **Latitude** – in decimal degrees.
- **Longitude** – in decimal degrees.
- **Total HW IQR (m)** – HW variability as shown in Figures 6b and 7b.
- **Exceedance levels (m above datum)** - for each ARI threshold level, for each epoch.
- **Delta uMSL ($\Delta\mu_{MSL}$) (m)** – the difference in epoch MSL between epochs.
- **Delta H (ΔH) (m)** – the difference in each ARI threshold level between epochs.
- **Delta F (ΔF) (multiplier)** – the difference in exceedance frequency between epochs.
- **Exceedances (# in epoch 1)** – the number of expected and observed exceedances counted above each epoch 1 ARI threshold level during epoch 1, including the number observed when each threshold is shifted ± 1 cm.
- **Exceedances (# in epoch 2)** – the number of expected and observed exceedances counted above each epoch 1 ARI threshold level during epoch 2, including the number observed when each threshold is shifted ± 1 cm.